

Devastating Consequences

Martin Jukes, November 5th, 2025

It is now inevitable that we will overshoot the 1.5°C target. António Guterres has affirmed[1] as much and talked of "devastating consequences".

We are not just passing this target, we are passing it while accelerating towards higher temperatures.

It is difficult to get a clear view of what the devastation will be. A recent report on Planetary Solvency (Trust et al., 2025) noted that some policy makers still make use of damage estimates from Nordhaus and Boyer (2000), presumably unaware of just how far the scientific understanding of risk thresholds has changed since then. The Trust et al report concludes that 2.0°C warming by 2050, which is our current trajectory, will result in "Catastrophic mortality events from disease, nutrition, thirst and conflict", with more than 2 billion deaths, and "Breakdown of some critical ecosystem services".

The "critical ecosystem services" referred to above include the partial absorption of pollutants that we spew out into the atmosphere. There are already signs that some significant ecosystem services are already going into reverse and, rather than retarding warming by absorbing greenhouse gasses, starting to accelerate warming by releasing them. The fact that these reversals may reach significant scale before we have implemented any effective control of our emissions goes beyond devastation.

It is no longer enough to reduce emissions. Our reduction in emissions and implementation of systems to extract greenhouse gasses from the atmosphere needs to outpace the breakdown of ecosystem services.

The Trust et al assessment is not without its uncertainties, but the evidence of breakdown of ecosystem services is extensive and persuasive.

It is a devastating situation, a devastating failure of decades of efforts to bring our emissions under control.

It is extremely tempting, especially for those who have worked for decades to effect change, to look for the cause of this devastating failure in the actions of others. But, if we really want to make the massive change needed between now and 2050, we have to look deeper.

We need to find, nurture, sustain hope.

The picture above shows a solitary red kite circling above the Chilterns. Watching it on a Sunday afternoon I felt some hope. It is hard to say where this came from, but it is there. There is hope in the enthusiasm of so many to make a positive change, and in the increasing numbers of people who are making life and career choices based on the belief in a sustainable future.

[1] Guardian interview, 2025/10/28. www.theguardian.com/environment/2025/oct/28/change-course-now-humanity-has-missed-15c-climate-target-says-un-head

[2] Trust et al. 2025. global-tipping-points.org/planetary-solvency/

[3] William D. Nordhaus, Joseph Boyer, 2000: Warming the World: Economic Models of Global Warming. direct.mit.edu/books/monograph/2697/Warming-the-WorldEconomic-Models-of-Global-Warming